

A Descriptive Study to Assess the Knowledge Regarding New Born Care among Postnatal Mother's with a View to Prepare a Pamphlet in SGT Hospital Gurugram

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ABSTRACT

In many communities around the world, newborn deaths are so common that children are not even named until they survive their first month of life. Children are an embodiment of our dreams and hopes for the future. For a nation to grow and progress, the well being and the health of the children is of crucial importance. Advances in medical research, the advent of new technologies have helped improve the healthcare of both well and sick newborn babies. Further innovation in baby care equipment have made the task of caring for babies much easier. Care practices immediately after delivery play a major role in causing neonatal morbidities and mortalities. Insufficient knowledge of parents regarding essential newborn care leads to decrease in the quality care. The investigators felt a real need to assess the mother's knowledge regarding essential newborn care. The objectives of the study were to assess the knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding essential newborn care and to develop a pamphlet on new born care. A descriptive study with non-experimental research design was adopted. Sixty postnatal mothers admitted in postnatal ward of SGT hospital, Gurugram were selected using convenient sampling technique from 16/04 to 22/04/2019. The tool used was structured questionnaire. The study findings revealed that majority (63.3%) of the postnatal mothers had satisfactory knowledge scores and only 10% postnatal mothers had inadequate knowledge scores, whereas rest 26.6 % of the subjects had inadequate knowledge regarding essential newborn care. A pamphlet regarding essential newborn care was disseminated to postnatal mothers.

KEYWORDS: knowledge, post natal mothers, newborn care

INTRODUCTION

Children are an embodiment of our dreams and hopes for the future. For a nation to grow and progress, the well being and the health of the children is of crucial importance. Today, babies have more opportunities than ever before to grow into healthy children, adolescents and adults. Advances in medical research, the advent of new technologies have helped improve the healthcare of both well and sick newborn babies. Further innovation in baby care equipment have made the task of caring for babies much easier.¹

A neonate is a newborn infant, especially one less than four weeks old. Mother's knowledge on neonatal care and practice accordingly plays an important role in bringing down the mortality as well as morbidity. Skilled professional care during pregnancy, at birth and during the postnatal period is as crucial for the newborn baby as its mother package of newborn care practices exists, which has a proven impact on reducing mortality. Child birth and the neonatal period are culturally important times, during which there is strong adherence to traditional practices.²

The normal practices of neonatal care include breastfeeding, maintenance of body temperature, baby massage, skincare and baby bath, care of the umbilical stump, care of eyes, dresses for the baby, immunization practices. Many potentially harmful newborn care practices are being carried

How to cite this paper: Ms. Sumyra Nazir | Ms. Monica | Mr. Mohit "A Descriptive Study to Assess the Knowledge Regarding New Born Care among Postnatal Mother's with a View to Prepare a Pamphlet in SGT Hospital Gurugram" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-2, February 2020, pp.1069-1073, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd30088.pdf

IJTSRD30088

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out such as unhygienic cord cutting, delayed breastfeeding and early bathing this was found out by a study which was conducted in 2005 in rural Karnataka with an objective to determine the healthy and harmful practices regarding neonatal care. It explores local newborn practices and beliefs, analyses their harmful or beneficial characteristics. They conducted a prospective survey following mothers through their experience of pregnancy and postnatal period. The study area consists of 11 villages with a population of about 6000 households' sound knowledge on neonatal care and early detection of danger signs and seeking medical help from appropriate centers could lower the mortality and morbidity. Mother is the closest person to a neonate. Knowledge of mothers on neonatal care and proper practice of that knowledge could help many unexpected situations.^{3,4}

NEED OF THE STUDY

As per the Sample Registration System (SRS 2008), the Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) for India has been declining over the years and has declined from 57 per thousand live births in 2006 to 53 per thousand live births in 2008. In Karnataka it has been 48 per thousand live births in 2006 to 45 per thousand live births in 2008. In view of the high death rate in the newborn period, it's imperative that concerned efforts should be made to educate the health personnel and the public to improve health of the newborn. India has the

highest infant mortality rate in the world, a nationwide survey reveals. India has slipped from 128 to 134 ranks in 2009 according to a United Nations Human Development report. Save the Children, a voluntary group reports one infant dies every 15 seconds in the country. Over 4 lakh newborns die in the first 24 hours of their life and 90 per cent of deaths are due to preventable diseases like pneumonia and diarrhea. Under five mortality has decreased in recent years but most of it's due to a decrease in the post neonatal mortality. Newborn care practice at and immediately following delivery can contribute to morbidity and mortality in neonates. A set of essential newborn care (ENC) practices have been proven to reduce the risk. So it's very essential that the mothers need to be aware of the newborn care. Hence the researcher felt there is a need to improve knowledge on practices of mothers regarding neonatal care. Taking into account all the above facts the researcher felt to conduct an effectiveness of structured teaching programme about knowledge on practices of mothers regarding neonatal care in a selected hospital⁵.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

"A descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding newborn care among postnatal mother's with a view to prepare a pamphlet in SGT Hospital Gurugram."

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding newborn care.
2. To find out the association between the knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding newborn care and their selected personal variables.
3. Develop a pamphlet on neonatal care.

HYPOTHESIS:

H1-There will be a significant association between level of knowledge and their selected personal variables.

RESEARCH APPROACH

The research approach involves the description of the plan to investigate the phenomenon under study⁵. The approach helps to decide about the presence and absence as well as manipulation and control over variables. The choice of approach depends upon the purpose of study.

In the present study a descriptive research approach is considered more appropriate to accomplish the objectives of the study.

RESERCH DESIGN

The research design is the master plan specifying the methods and procedures for collecting and analysing the needed information in the research study⁶.

The research design selected for the study is non experimental research design.

VARIABLES UNDER STUDY:

Research Variables:

Knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding newborn care.

Demographic Variables:

Demographic variables of postnatal mothers include their age in years, educational status, occupation, religion, type of family, family income per month, previous exposure to any information regarding new born care.

SETTING OF THE STUDY:

The setting is the physical location and condition in which data collection take place. The study was conducted on SGT hospital , Gurugram.

POPULATION:

In the present study, population comprises of postnatal mothers who are admitted in postnatal ward.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLE SIZE:

In the presence study, sample size is 60 postnatal mothers.

SAMPLIG TECHNIQUE:

Non probability convenience sampling technique was used for selecting 60 postnatal mothers for the present study.

SAMPLING CRITERIA:

Inclusion Criteria

Postnatal mothers who are

1. Available during data collection.
2. Willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

Postnatal mothers those who are sick and not willing to participate.

DATA COLLECTION TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES

The most important and crucial aspect of any investigation is the collection of appropriate information, which provides necessary data for the study.

A structured knowledge questionnaire can be used to assess the knowledge regarding newborn care among postnatal mothers

DESCRIPTION OF TOOL

THE TOOL CONSIST OF –

Section A – It consists of 7question on selected demographic variables of the postnatal mothers such as

Age, Education, Marital status, Family income, Type of community, Number of children, Previous knowledge.

Section B – It consists of total 25 questions on knowledge regarding newborn care.

Criteria Measures

Each question has 4option with one correct answer. For each question the correct response carries 'one' mark and wrong answer carries 'zero' mark.

SCORING

MAXIMUM SCORE – 25

MINIMUM SCORE – 0

PROCEDURE FOR FINAL DATA COLLECTION

The tool used to collect the data from the samples was structured interview schedule. The structured interview schedule was administered to seek information on demographic data of the respondents and to collect data on knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding essential newborn care after taking written consent from them from 16/04 to 22/04/2019. Following data collection, pamphlet regarding essential newborn care were disseminated to the subjects

ORGANIZATION OF INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The data obtained during data collection was summarized in the master data sheets, analysed, tabulated and interpreted according to the objectives. The data was organized and presented under following sections:

Section I -Description of sample characteristics :

- Frequency and percentage distribution of sample characteristics

Section II:Findings related to distributions of knowledge among studied sample:

Section III. Findings related to association of knowledge with selected factors age, education, family income, community, number of children and previous knowledge.

- Chi square computed to establish the association between the knowledge scores and selected variables.

SECTION I DESCRIPTION OF SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS

This section describes the characteristics of postnatal mothers. The characteristics included in the study were age, The frequency and percentage were computed for describing the above.

Table1:Frequency and percentage distribution of Demographical characteristics in samples by age, education, family income, community, number of children and previous knowledge.

N=60

S.NO	SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC DATA	FREQUENCY (F)	PERCENTAGE(%)
1	Age		
	20-25	34	56.66%
	26-30	19	31.66%
	31-35	7	11.66%
2	Educational status		
	Primary	16	26.66%
	Matriculation	24	40%
	Senior secondary	10	16.66%
3	Graduate	10	16.66%
	Family monthly income		
	10000-15000	27	45%
4	15000-20000	20	33.33%
	Above 20000	13	21.66%
4	Community		
	Urban	18	30%
	Rural	42	70%
5	Number of children		
	One	23	38.33%
	Two	34	56.66%
	More than two	3	5%
6	Previous knowledge		
	Yes	40	66.66%
	No	20	33.33%

- Data presented in table 1 shows that majority of the sample (56.66%) were in the age group of 20-25 years.
- Most of the sample(40%) were having matriculation as their educational status.
- Data further reveals that majority of the sample (45%) were having family income between 10000-15000.
- Majority of the sample (70%) belongs to rural community.
- Data in the table further shows that most of the sample (56.6%)were having two children.
- Data further revealed that 66.6% of the sample were having previous knowledge about newborn care.

Table2 Section II : Findings related to distributions of knowledge among studied sample :

N=60

S.NO	SOCIALDEMOGRAPHIC DATA	FREQUENCY(F)	PERCENTAGE(%)
1	Inadequate(1-7)	6	10.1%
2	Satisfactory(8-16)	38	63.3%
3	Adequate(17-25)	16	26.6%

- Data presented in table 2. reveals that majority(63.3%) of postnatal mothers had satisfactory knowledge and (10%) mothers have inadequate knowledge regarding newborn care.

Table 3 Section III. Findings related to association of knowledge with selected factors age, education, family income, community, number of children and previous knowledge.

➤ Chi square computed to establish the association between the knowledge scores and selected variables.

S.NO	Sample Characteristics	df	Obtained Chi Square value (X ²)	Table value of Chi square
1	Age (in Years)	2	26.049 ^s	5.991
	20-25			
	26-30			
	31-35			
2	Educational status	3	53.7 ^s	7.815
	Primary			
	Matriculation			
	Senior secondary Graduation			
3	community	1	24.9 ^s	3.841
	Rural			
	Urban			
4	Monthly income	2	39.4 ^s	5.991
	10000-15000			
	15000-20000			
	Above 20000			
5	No. of children	2	24.3 ^s	5.991
	One			
	Two			
	More than two			

S= significant at 0.05 level
NS = not significant at 0.05 level

➤ Data presented in Table 3 shows that chi square value of age is 26.05, for educational status (53.7), community (24.9), monthly income (39.4) and number of children (24.3) at df 2,3,1,2,2 respectively.

This shows that chi square is significant for all demographic variables at 0.05 level of significance.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY
FINDINGS RELATED TO THE DESCRIPTION OF SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS

- Data shows that majority of the sample (56.66%) were in the age group of 20-25 years.
- Most of the sample(40%) were having matriculation as their educational status.
- Data further reveals that majority of the sample (45%) were having family income between 10000-15000.
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Findings related to distributions of knowledge among studied sample:

- Data. reveals that majority(63.3%) of postnatal mothers had satisfactory knowledge and (10%) mothers have inadequate knowledge regarding newborn care.

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income (39.4) and number of children (24.3) at df 2,3,1,2,2 respectively.

- This shows that chi square is significant for all demographic variables at 0.05 level of significance.

CONCLUSION :

Most maternal education on essential newborn care was received during pregnancy. Maternal education on essential newborn care was adequate with regards to eye care, care of the low birth weight, thermoregulation and immunization. Knowledge gaps existed among postnatal mothers with regards to eye care, cord care and immunisation. Health education on essential newborn care practices should be integrated into routine antenatal services and re-emphasised in the postnatal period to help improve maternal knowledge and towards essential newborn care.

DISCUSSION:

The present study was aimed to assess the knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding essential newborn care in SGT Hospital, Gurugram.

In the present study majority of mothers had adequate knowledge on newborn care. The findings are supported by a survey study conducted in 2006 which revealed that mothers' knowledge and practices were within good and satisfactory average scores in most of the studied items related to newborn care given at home except breast

feeding⁷. The study findings also revealed that mothers with higher educational status had better knowledge. Similar findings are reported in other studies also⁸. Based on the findings of the study it is concluded that postnatal mothers admitted in SGT hospital had adequate knowledge on newborn care.

To find the association of knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding essential newborn care with various socio-demographic variables. The association of level of knowledge regarding newborn care among postnatal mothers with selected socio-demographic Variables like age, education, community and number of children were statistically significant at 0.05% level of significance. In conformity to these finding, a similar study was conducted to assess the knowledge and practices of newborn care among postnatal mothers in tertiary care hospital of Udupi District which revealed that education status of the mothers had significant association with the knowledge of mothers regarding newborn care. Other demographic variables like age (in years), No. of children, religion did not show any statistically significant association with knowledge score of the mothers.⁹

IMPLICATIONS:

The findings of the present study have implications for nursing education, nursing practice, nursing administration, nursing research and general education.

Nursing Education

Nurses working in clinical as well as community set up need to understand the importance of essential newborn care and educate the expectant, postnatal mothers and their family members about its influence in their baby's health. Midwives and nurses working in the postnatal wards and OPD maternity department can facilitate their service in providing knowledge regarding essential newborn care and parent counselling to promote it to reduce child health problems thereby contributing to a reduction in infant mortality rate.

Nursing Administration

Nursing administration should take initiation in organizing In Service Education Programme for nurses in order to keep them abreast with the updates in Essential Newborn Care and should also encourage them to participate in such type of activities by providing them adequate resources.

Nursing Practice

Health care personnel should be given an opportunity to update their knowledge regarding essential newborn care, and to educate and provide adequate knowledge to mothers. Every student nurse should be given a learning experience during her training to plan and conduct health education for mothers and family members on essential newborn care.

Nursing Research

There is a need for nursing research in the biophysiological areas of motherhood. It is important to know about the mother's knowledge regarding essential newborn care because children are the key to the development of the whole nation. Nurses need to collect data regarding the knowledge level of mothers and further should take measures to improve their knowledge by conducting planned teaching programmes.

General Education

Educating mothers regarding Essential Newborn Care plays a key role in saving the best investment of a country for its future.

LIMITATIONS:

- This study was a based on reported rather than observed knowledge towards newborn care practices. There was therefore a risk that mothers may report what was expected of them but their actual practices may be different.
- Lack of a universal census on definition of good or poor knowledge posed a challenge in the study.
- As the study was carried out among postnatal mothers in SGT Hospital, findings may not be generalised to the whole country.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Health education on essential newborn care practices should be integrated into routine antenatal services and re-emphasised in the postnatal period to help improve maternal knowledge and towards essential newborn care practices.
- The setting and sample were selected on convenient basis limits its generalizability. There is need to carry out a large scale study to explore the different practices adopted by the mothers to provide best care to their babies.
- Awareness programmes may be formalized on the basis of present study.

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